

COMMUNICATION AND INNOVATION ADOPTION IN THE AKADEP EXTENSION SYSTEM IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study examines the contributions of communication in influencing innovation adoption of the Akwa Ibom State Agriculture Development Programme (AKADEP) extension system among farmers in Akwa Ibom State. Survey research was adopted for the study with population of 531,123 farmers in Itu L.G.A. from where the sample size of 399 was selected. Data for the study were collected using structured questionnaire, and were analysed through frequency distribution and simple percentages. Findings showed that many communication channels (such as electronic media, women group meetings, AKADEP agents, town criers, community influencers, etc.) were adopted in disseminating information about innovation adoption in AKADEP extension system among selected farmers. Communication enhances the adoption of innovation in AKADEP in informing farmers of innovation, educating them on how to adopt the innovation, enlightening them on the need to adopt the innovation, persuading them to adopt innovation, among others. To a great extent (42%), communication influenced the adoption of innovation in AKADEP extension system in Akwa Ibom State. Other than mass communication, other factors like productivity, high profit made by the adopters of the innovation, fear of not being allowed to partake in future initiatives by government on agriculture also influenced the adoption of the innovation. It was concluded that communication is essential in innovation adoption. The paper, therefore, recommends, among others, that communication should be sustained in continually propagating innovation adoption messages to the farmers in rural communities; there should be a conscious effort to make full use of social media, combined with electronic media in the dissemination of innovation messages among others.

Keywords: Innovations, Adoption, Innovation Adoption, AKADEP, Communication, Communication System, Communication Strategies.

Introduction

Man is constantly faced with innovations in his attempt to overcome barriers and difficulties imposed by nature. The extent to which he succeeds in this attempt determines his level of development. Availability and the willingness to adopt innovations jointly account for the difference in development levels of various societies. And so, the adoption of innovations is, therefore, of utmost importance to any society. Whether developed or developing, a society is in continuous need of social, economic or technological change as old methods need to be replaced with new and better ones.

In the submission of König, Blömeke, Paine, Schmidt and Hsieh (2011), all attempts aimed at changing attitude and behaviour involve educative processes because in order to change, people must first acquire fresh knowledge, insights and skills, and then learn about the subject of change. Such fresh knowledge, skills and insight, in most cases, are consciously sought after by those who appreciate the need for innovations and are well disposed towards change. In other words, exposure to such knowledge, skills and insights may not be conscious. However, the process constitutes learning, attitude change and decision facilitated by communication.

McQuail and Windahl (2016) in explaining some features of Rogers and Shoemaker's paradigm of innovation, "diffusion process", argue that diffusion of innovation does involves different communication sources - general mass media, advertising or processional materials, official agencies of change, informal social contacts, etc. Thus, mass media and advertising are so important in the decision to adopt or not, while the experience of usage of the innovation may serve as the main source of confirmation or rejection.

It is, therefore, arguable that the correlation between innovation adoption and development has informed the shift in emphasis from the conventional communication paradigms to developmental communication/journalism by most third world countries. Developmental communication is thought of as a means of aiding overall national consciousness and development. Advocates of this form of communication believe that it is a journalism of hope and change, seeking to persuade the people that their happiness and emancipation lie on and enhanced by the adoption of innovations.

In Nigeria, for instance, development needs continue to spread into different areas of national life including the agricultural sector. In this area, where most of the studies in innovation adoption have been carried out (McQuail and Windahl, 2016), the World

Bank in assisting developing countries improve their agriculture, has pioneered a system of extension delivery which accounts for the adoption of new and improved farming practices in many states including Akwa Ibom, championed by AKADEP.

The AKADEP Extension System, as a new idea for reforming agricultural extension, adopted the *Training and Visit* system introduced by Daniel Benor and James Harrison in their booklet titled “*Agricultural Extension: The Training and Visit System*” (The World Bank, 1977). This system has been adopted (implicitly or explicitly) by some forty developing countries in Asia, Africa, Europe and Central and South America. In Africa, for instance, Nigeria adopted the system in conjunction with the Agricultural Development Projects (ADPs) in all the states of the federation, assisted by the World Bank.

The aim of the programme was to assist in building a professional extension service that is capable of supporting farmers to raise production, increase income and also provide appropriate backing for agricultural development. According to the programme initiators, the extension reviewed existing traditional agricultural practices and identified areas of deficiency, which prompted strategic research into these areas with a view to developing improved farming techniques that will ultimately lead to higher yields. The research made recommendations which provided new practices and forms of agricultural techniques that could take agriculture to another level.

The connection between the extension system and the practical application of the extension system’s requirements lied on the extent to which the innovative ideas and recommendations were adopted by local farmers in Akwa Ibom State. This highlights the significance of communication as a tool for driving the adoption of the agricultural innovation in the system. How communication played the pivotal role in that process, forms the crux of this study.

Statement of the Research Problem

The Akwa Ibom Agricultural Development Programme (AKADEP) extension system was one of the few innovations in Agriculture aimed at boosting food security in Akwa Ibom State through improved practices in Agriculture. As in other states of the Nigerian federation, AKADEP, a creation from the Cross-River State Development Programme (CRADP) in 1988, assumed the responsibility of facilitating, ensuring and supporting local farmers with the knowledge, skills, practices and materials for improving food production, and by extension, food security in the state and country at large.

Observation by the researchers showed that many farmers in the state adopted the innovations of the AKADEP for better food production. Observation also showed that different media of communication like radio, television, newspapers, etc. were used in disseminating information about the programme and the advantage(s) of adopting those new agricultural practices.

While it is true that communication media were actively used in the dissemination of information about the AKADEP in the state and farmers in Itu Local Government Area also adopted the innovations on Agriculture, it is not clear whether the adoption was engineered by the media's involvement in the process of informing and educating the farmers in the state. At the moment, research studies that clearly establish the extent of communication being a causal agent in the process of innovation adoption, seems to be lacking. This has created a knowledge gap that should be filled, hence, this research.

Objectives of the Study

This study sought to:

1. find out the communication channels adopted in disseminating information about innovation adoption in AKADEP extension system among selected farmers in Akwa Ibom State;
2. examine the role of communication in enhancing adoption of innovation in AKADEP extension system among selected farmers in Akwa Ibom State;
3. determine the extent to which communication influenced the adoption of innovation in AKADEP extension system among selected farmers in Akwa Ibom State;
4. determine other factors other than mass communication that affected the adoption of innovation in AKADEP extension system among selected farmers in Akwa Ibom State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the conduct of this study:

1. What were the communication channels adopted in disseminating information about innovation adoption in AKADEP extension system among selected farmers in Akwa Ibom State?
2. What were the contribution(s) of communication in enhancing the adoption of innovation in AKADEP extension system among selected farmers in Akwa Ibom State?
3. To what extent did communication influence the adoption of innovation in

- AKADEP extension system among selected farmers in Akwa Ibom State?
4. Other than mass communication, what other factors affected the adoption of innovation in AKADEP extension system among selected farmers in Akwa Ibom State?

Delimitation of the Study

This study focused on the adoption of agricultural innovations championed by the Akwa Ibom State Agricultural Development Programme (AKADEP). The innovations referred to in this study were: the use of fertilizers, the use of improved planting materials (seeds, stems, etc.), and planting in rows. The study also considered only the farmers in Itu Local Government Areas who engage in active commercial farming and adopt the above farming practices as specified by the AKADEP extension system. Any other farmers outside the above were exempted in this study.

Definition of Terms

The following terms were defined in the context of this study:

Communication means all the channels, methods and processes used in disseminating information about the AKADEP agricultural extension system to farmers in Akwa Ibom State.

Innovation Adoption means all the processes by which new ideas and practices of agriculture under the AKADEP agricultural extension programme are used by the farmers in Akwa Ibom State, as compared to the old ways of agriculture.

Innovation refers to those improvements on or replacements of old farming practices made available by the AKADEP extension system for farmers in Akwa Ibom State.

AKADEP refers to the Akwa Ibom Agricultural Development Project instituted as a system with innovative practices to enhance the production and improvement of agriculture in Akwa Ibom State.

Literature Review

Akwa Ibom State Agricultural Development Programme (AKADEP)

Akwa Ibom Agricultural Development Programme (AKADEP) was excised from the Cross-River State Agricultural Development Programme (CRADP) after the creation of Akwa Ibom State (AKS) from the former Cross River State (CRS) in

September, 1987. Until recently, AKADEP concentrated most of its development efforts on arable crops production. But due to the significant shortfall in animal protein in the diet of its local population, AKADEP had in the last five years intensified its development efforts in the area of fish production, agro-forestry and food processing. Besides, a balanced agricultural development should include not only crop, but also animal production, since proteins in diet are necessary for human health (Iwuchukwu and Igbokwe, 2013).

Before the creation of Agricultural Development Programmes (ADP), the Nigerian government formulated series of agricultural policies and programmes from the post-colonial era to the civil war period (1st October 1960 to 15th January 1966). During this period, policies were formulated to actualize more equitable growth in agriculture. The pre-independence policy of surplus extraction had translated into the demarcation of the country into the Western Region (Cocoa), the Northern Region (Groundnut) and the Eastern Region (Oil palm). At that time, manufacturing organizations were considered the best method of achieving industrialization in the country.

But it was mind-boggling that in spite of the ambitious agricultural policies formulated, there were no corresponding programmes, projects, initiatives or schemes with which to actualize these lofty agricultural development policies. The National Fadama Development Project (NFDP) was designed in the 1990s to promote low-cost improved irrigation technology under World Bank financing. One of the major objectives of the Fadama Programme was to increase the sustainability of the income of Fadama users through the expansion of farm and non-farm activities.

In spite of all these agricultural development policies and programmes, Nigeria faces acute food shortage. AKADEP was set up to effectively contain this problem and many more in the state, and the programme has recorded relative success vis-à-vis other agricultural programmes, in its efforts address to food insecurity.

Communication

According to Clemes, Gan and Du (2012), communication informs and persuades people about services provided by an organisation or new ways of doing things in such a way that a specific practice offers the best solution to people's needs, reminds them of service/product availability, and inspires them to action. Choi and Whinston (2000) view communication as a process in which participants create and share information with one another in order to reach a mutual understanding. They further state that:

This newness of the idea in the message content gives diffusion its special character. The newness means that some degree of uncertainty is involved in diffusion. Uncertainty is the degree to which a number of alternatives are perceived with respect to the occurrence of an event and the relative probability of these alternatives. Uncertainty implies a lack of predictability, of structure, of information. In fact, information is a means of reducing uncertainty. Information is a difference in matter-energy that affects uncertainty in a situation where a choice exists among a set of alternatives (Choi and Whinston, 2000, p. 10).

Innovation

Innovation is an important phenomenon in any modern economy; it allows firms to adopt new and better processes of performing their operations. Innovation refers (in this case) to all of the processes by which ideas are generated and converted into useful products and services for which there is an economic value or cost and people are willing to pay for. In the financial service industry, innovation is viewed as the act of creating and popularizing new or reformed financial instruments, technologies, institutions and markets which facilitate access to information, trading and means of payment (Akinwumi, 2016). Innovation generally is critical for development of firms and individuals portraying new ideas, quality and convenience.

Nofie (2011) asserts that innovation in the financial sector is the arrival of a new or better product and or process that lowers the cost of producing existing financial services or transactions. Financial innovations are used by banks as formidable strategic variables to outstrip the competition and have become an essential means for the banks to improve their performance, as well as grow and maintain their effectiveness in the market (Batiz-Lazo and Woldesenbet, 2006). In a highly turbulent environment, a successful innovation, driven by technology, can create a unique competitive position and gives a bank a competitive advantage and leads to superior financial performance (Roberts and Amit, 2003).

Technological innovations involve improvement on something already existing. In the 20th century, innovations in semi-conductor technology increased the performance of electronic materials and devices by a factor of a million, while decreasing the cost an achievement unparalleled in the history of any technology (Rogers, 1981). The advances in telecommunication technologies in the past 25 years have had a profound impact on the nature of banking and the way banks and other financial institutions are organized (Choi and Whinston, 2000).

Theoretical Framework

Diffusion of Innovation Theory

According to Rogers (2003), the factors which influence the diffusion of an innovation include: relative advantage (the extent to which a technology offers improvements over currently available tools), compatibility (its consistency with social practices and norms among its users), complexity (its ease of use or learning), trialability (the opportunity to try an innovation before committing to use it), and observability (the extent to which the technology's outputs and its gains are clear to see). These elements are not mutually exclusive and thus, may not predict either the extent or the rate of innovation diffusion or adoption.

Rogers' theory does not tell us whether the system of organisations need to be in normal operating mode in order for the theory to apply or whether the theory holds in all types of organisations or only in certain types. Specifically, the theory begins to describe the innovation-decision process within organisations but not to the level of addressing whether and how the characteristics of an innovation interact to affect its adoption within organisations, or whether organisational type, size or industry affect adoption.

Anyasi and Otubu (2009) defined diffusion as the process of communicating an innovation through certain channels over a certain period of time among the groups of a social system. They also defined communication as a process where people create and share information among one another to reach a mutual understanding. Porteous (2006) states that there are four stages in innovation diffusion process; invention, diffusion (or communication) through the social system, time and consequences. The ease of use and novelty of an innovation can determine the way an individual will respond to it.

It is believed that an innovation with relative advantage, cost savings with less complexity will be adopted easily and faster by an individual. Information Technology diffusion, for instance, involves more than acquiring computers and microelectronics-based gadgets and related know-how. It involves preparedness and development of technical change- generating capability to adapt given technology to diverse needs. In advanced market economies, where large volume and value of goods are traded, the modern banking system provides an efficient payment mechanism for settlement of claims through banks. Access into a globalised economy would only be through IT inputs (personal computer, internet, email, and others), provided there is enabling facilities and constant power supply. Companies

are now in a better position to respond speedily to change in demand patterns and change in international comparative advantages, courtesy of telecommunication technology (Bamidele, 2006).

The theory highlights the use of new ideas in achieving aims as a complete or partial departure from the old ways of doing things. Since this study considered the use of communication to influence innovation adoption by the AKADEP, the theory was useful in explaining the process of innovation adoption in the agricultural extension practices of farmers in Itu local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State.

Research Methodology

a. Research Design

Since the study involves people - their beliefs, pinions, attitudes and preferences - the survey method was adopted for the investigation as it appeared to be most appropriate research technique in this context. Survey was adopted in this study because of the high population of farmers in Akwa Ibom State, which constituted serious complexity in reaching and seeking the opinions of all on the matter under study.

b. Population of the Study

The population of this study consisted of all the farmers in Itu Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. Itu was selected because of the perceived high agricultural activities in the area. The population of Itu according to the National Bureau of Statistics (2020), is 531,123. This was used as the population of this study.

c. Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The sample size for this study was 399 respondents determined using the Taro Yamane sampling formula. In sampling the respondents, multistage sampling techniques was used. First, the availability sampling technique was used to sample 99 staff from the Ministry of Agriculture Office in Itu. In the second stage, the purposive sampling technique was used to select 300 farmers in Oku Iboko axis, Mbak Atia axis and Old Town axis. The reason for sampling these three villages was their high involvement in farming activities and adoption of the innovations of AKADEP extension system.

d. Instrument for Data Collection

The data for this study were collected using a structured questionnaire. The items on the questionnaire were arranged in a single section that focused on answering the research questions of the study.

e. **Method of Data Collection and Analysis**

Data for this study were collected by the researchers with the assistance of 3 research assistants. The collection exercise lasted for five days. The data were analysed using frequency distribution and simple percentages, and this reduced the data into...

Presentation and Discussion of Findings

Table 1: Communication Media from which selected Farmers learnt about AKADEP’s Innovation in Itu LGA

Communication Media	Frequency	Percentages
Print Media (Newspapers, Books, flyers, etc.)	-	
Electronic Media (Radio, Television etc.)	39	11
Social Media (Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp, etc.)	-	-
Traditional Media (Town criers, Opinion leaders and Influencers	88	26
Women groups and other village groups’ meetings	91	27
Advocacy Programmes by AKADEP agents in village halls	101	29
	26	7
Total	345	100

The data on Table 1 shows the various media used in propagating the innovations in agriculture by AKADEP to the farmers in Itu LGA of Akwa Ibom State. The data have revealed that meetings with women groups with 29% response rate was the most viable communication channel through which the respondents accessed information on the innovation from the agricultural agency. This was followed by opinion leaders and influencers in the communities with 27% response rate, followed by traditional medium of town crying with response rate of 26%, followed by electronic media (radio and TV) with response rate of 11% while the advocacy programmes by AKADEP staff was the medium with the least message reception by the farmers under study. The finding also showed that social media has no

contribution on the adoption of innovations among the farmers in the communities under study.

Table 2: Most Effective Medium at the First Try Out of the Innovation

Most Effective Communication Medium	Frequency	Percentage
Radio “The former”	48	14
TV	-	-
Newspaper/Magazine	-	-
Social Media	-	-
Village source and groups	43	13
Contact farmer	84	24
Extension agents	170	49
Total	345	100

Table 2 shows that extension agent of about 170 (49%) influenced the decision to try out the innovations, followed by the contact farmer with frequency of 84 (24%), and the radio with frequency of 48 (14%) while village sources and groups had the least effectiveness with 13%.

Table 3: Contribution(s) of Communication in enhancing the Adoption of Innovation in AKADEP Extension System among Selected Farmers in Akwa Ibom State

Responses	Frequency	Percentages
Enlightening farmers on new farming practices	91	26
Education of farmers on how to adopt new practices	65	19
Reinforcing the need to adopt new farming innovations	45	13
Informing farmers on the gains of innovation	61	18

Persuasion of farmers to try the new Agric innovations	83	24
Total	345	100

Table 3 shows the various contributions of communication in the adoption of the agricultural innovations of AKADEP extension system. The table revealed 26% of the respondents agreed that communication enlightened them on new farming practices, 24% of the respondents were persuaded to try the innovation because of communication, 19% were educated on how to adopt the innovations, and 18% were informed on the advantage of adopting the innovations, while 13% were reinforced on the need to adopt the innovations.

Table 4: Extent to which Communication helped selected Farmers in Adoption of Innovation in AKADEP Extension System in Akwa Ibom State

Responses	Frequency	Percentages
Very Great Extent	71	20
Great Extent	145	42
Reasonable Extent	78	23
Little Extent	45	13
No Extent At all	6	2
Total	345	100

Table 4 shows 145 (42%) respondents agreed that communication to a great extent influenced their adoption of the innovation.

Table 5: Other than Mass Communication, other Factors that affected the Adoption of Innovation in AKADEP Extension System among Selected Farmers in Akwa Ibom State

Other factors	Frequency	Percentages
High Productivity from other adopters of the innovation	129	37
Fear of being tagged recalcitrant to innovations by other farmers	31	9

Profitability of the innovation as shown by adopters	126	37
Fear of Arrest by Government	-	-
Fear of extradition from community	8	2
Fear of being denied participation in subsequent government initiatives	51	15
Total	345	100

Table 5 shows that there are other factors other than communication that also influenced the adoption of the AKADEP innovations among the sampled farmers in Akwa Ibom State. The findings showed that improvement in productivity and high profit made by the adopters of the innovation influenced the adoption of the innovation by 129 and 126, respectively, representing 37% of selected farmers. The finding also showed that the fear of being denied participation in subsequent government initiatives also influenced the adoption of the innovation by 15%, while 9% adopted innovation for fear of being tagged recalcitrant to innovation or development by other farmers in the communities.

Discussion of Findings

Research Question 1: What were the communication channels adopted in disseminating information about innovation adoption in AKADEP extension system among selected farmers in Akwa Ibom State?

In answering this research question, the data on Table 1 were used. The data on the table indicated that there were many channels of communication through which information on the innovations in agriculture by AKADEP were shared to the farmers in Itu L.G.A. of Akwa Ibom State.

According to the table, electronic media, meetings with women groups, town crier, opinion leaders, AKADEP extension agents, and other influencers were the main sources of information to the farmers. Here, meetings with women groups with 29% rated highest and most viable communication channel through which the respondents accessed information on the innovation from the agricultural agency.

This was followed by opinion leaders and influencers in the communities with 27% response rate, followed by traditional medium of town crying with response rate of 26%, and electronic media (radio and TV) with response rate of 11%.

The distribution also showed that the advocacy programmes by AKADEP staff was the medium with the least message reception by the farmers under study. In other words, AKADEP staff were not communicating as fast and much as the women groups in the communities under study. Beyond this, the finding also showed that social media has no contribution on the adoption of innovations among the farmers in the communities under study.

The findings above have shown the significant role of communication channels in any society as well as their role in the adoption of innovation of any kind among people in any society. Just like McLuhan argued that the message is the medium, so have the findings shown that the messages of communication are best disseminated and assimilated through the channels of communication.

The findings on Table 2 further explained the medium of communication with initial information and influence on the process of the innovation adoption. The table showed that extension agent influenced farmers' decisions to try out the innovations at about 49% and was followed by the contact farmer (24%), followed by the radio with 14% while village sources and groups had the least effectiveness with 13%. The findings imply that interpersonal communication channels are very important in the dissemination of information for innovation adoption.

The above findings align with the submissions of McQuail and Windahl (2016) on the effectiveness of communication when using the right source. For them, communication in times of change is most effective when the source of the information is most understood and accessible to the recipients of the message. In this instance, the channels of the innovation communication played a unique role.

The theory of innovation adoption explains some aspects of this finding. In times and in the process of innovation adoption, the innovation must first be communicated and this usually takes the first stage. Innovation messages are possibly adopted only when communicated to the targeted people. This is only done through the use of viable means of communication.

Research Question 2: What were the contributions of communication in enhancing the adoption of innovation in AKADEP extension system among selected farmers in Akwa Ibom State?

To ascertain how effective communication influenced the process and real adoption of the innovation under study, there was need to examine the role of communication in the entire process. This led to the formulation of the above question. In answering the research question, the data on Table 3 were used.

The distribution on that table showed that communication makes numerous contributions in the process of adopting the agricultural innovations of the AKADEP extension system. The table revealed 26% of respondents agreed that communication enlightened them on new farming practices, 24% respondents agreed that communication persuaded them to try the innovation because of communication, 19% of the respondents agreed that communication educated them on how to adopt the innovations, 18% of the respondents agreed that communication informed them on the advantage of adopting the innovations, while 13% of the respondents agreed that communication was useful in reinforcing the need to adopt the innovations

Communication, behavioural change and innovation adoption are interrelated so much that one leads to the other. Communication (as shown by the above findings), is useful in driving change and influencing innovation adoption. In the process, communication informs, educate, persuades, reinforces and enlightens the need for change. This underscores the importance of communication as captured by scholars in the discipline of human communication.

For instance, McQuail (2010) submits that the primary function of communication is information, education and enlightenment. This suggests that people are informed about issues of change and the need to adopt change through the use of communication. They are also educated on how to adopt the change through the use of communication. Through this process of information and education, they become sufficiently enlightened on the need for change and in the process, take conscious and informed decision on the expected change. Again, Folarin (2002) also discusses the importance of communication to include persuasion and enforcement. The scholar argues that through constant communication, messages are reinforced and persuasion takes place, leading to attitude and behavioural changes among people in societies.

The adoption of innovation theory again makes useful proposition here. According to Rogers and Shoemaker, the diffusion of innovation model is based on the assumption that the process is made up of four (4) stages. These are Knowledge, Persuasion, Decision and Confirmation in this sequence. The findings highlight the role of communication here in the process of adopting change. The theory acknowledges the place of information and message sharing in the process of adopting innovation for change. The theory argues that change is only possible when information about change passes through the processes of first encounter to change information through communication, to the time where the adoption takes place through knowledge and persuasion. This implies that communication makes change possible especially when the information on change is shared to inform, educate and persuade people to accept change.

Research Question 3: To what extent did communication influence the adoption of innovation in AKADEP extension system among selected farmers in Akwa Ibom State?

In answering this research question, the data on Table 4 were used. According to the distribution on the table, 145 respondents indicating 42% agreed that communication, to a great extent, influenced their adoption of the innovation presented by AKADEP extension system. The findings suggest that communication plays a crucial role in the adoption of the innovation in the agricultural sector of the state.

The above findings are consistent with the one provided by Makosana (2014). The author examined the influence of communication on innovation adoption in banks and found a positive correlation between communication change adoption and innovation adoption. The findings also support the previous findings of the survey carried out by Akinwumi (2016). The study focused on the place of communication in the adoption of innovation among people. The findings of the study showed that communication was a prerequisite for effective process of innovation adoption.

Research Question 4: Other than mass communication, what other factors affected the adoption of innovation in AKADEP extension system among selected farmers in Akwa Ibom State?

The data on Table 5 were useful in answering this research question. The table showed that there are other factors other than communication that also influenced the

adoption of the AKADEP innovations among the sampled farmers in Akwa Ibom State. The findings showed that improvement in productivity and high profit made by the adopters of the innovation also influenced the adoption of the innovation by 37. The finding also showed that the fear of being denied participation in subsequent government initiatives also influenced adoption of innovation by 15%, while 9% adopted the innovation for fear of being tagged recalcitrant to innovation or development by other farmers in the communities.

The above finding suggests that communication functions with other factors or elements in society to bring about change. The innovation proposed by AKADEP was useful yet most farmers relied not only on communication as a tool for information, education and persuasion to adopt change, but also on the result of the change adopted by other people in society.

Here, the farmers in Itu Local Government area relied on the productivity of the innovation adopted by the other farmers. They also relied on the strength of the profits made by the other farmers before they adopted the change. Thus, the finding suggests that other factors were also responsible for the adoption of innovation among the farmers in Itu other than communication.

Summary of Findings

1. There were many communication channels adopted in disseminating information about innovation adoption in AKADEP extension system among selected farmers in Akwa Ibom State. These channels included electronic media, women group meetings, AKADEP agents, town criers, community influencers, etc.
2. Communication made some contributions in enhancing the adoption of innovation in AKADEP extension system among selected farmers in Akwa Ibom State. The contributions included informing farmers of innovation, educating them on how to adopt the innovation, enlightening them on the need to adopt the innovation, persuading them to adopt innovation, among others.
3. To a great extent (42%), communication influenced the adoption of innovation in AKADEP extension system among selected farmers in Akwa Ibom State.
4. Other than mass communication, other factors like productivity, high profit made by those who adopted the innovation, fear of not being allowed to partake in future initiatives by government on agriculture also influenced the adoption of the innovation in AKADEP extension system among selected farmers in Akwa Ibom State.

Conclusion

One of the numerous efforts of Nigerian government in tackling food insecurity in Nigeria is the initiation of various programmes aimed to be adopted among farmers at various locations in the country. In Akwa Ibom, the Akwa Ibom State Agricultural Development Programme (AKADEP) was one of the keenly implemented innovation intended to be adopted by farmers across the entire state. This programme was massively embraced by farmers in different locations in the state.

This study examined the influence of communication in the adoption of this Agric innovation by farmers in ITU local Government area of the state. The findings have led to the conclusion that communication, to a great extent, influenced the adoption of agricultural innovation championed by the AKADEP extension system.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this research, the following recommendations are made:

1. Considering the effectiveness of communication in the process of causing change, the use of communication should be sustained in continually propagating innovation adoption messages to the farmers in rural communities.
2. There should be a conscious effort to make full use of social media, combined with electronic media in the dissemination of innovation messages. This will further enforce adoption of innovation.
3. There is also a need for integrated communication approach to the dissemination of innovation adoption messages. Here, various approaches and strategies can be used to create awareness of the innovation and to ensure adoption of such innovations.

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